

Understanding the Paradigm Shift of ULFA: From Factional Differences to the Peace Accord

Madhusmita Konwar¹

Dr. Partha Pratim Baruah²

¹**Designation:** Research Scholar Department of Sociology, Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Vishwavidyalaya, Nagaon, Assam, India, e-mail: konwarmadhusmita3@gmail.com

²**Designation:** Assistant Professor, Department of Sociology, Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Vishwavidyalaya, Nagaon, Assam, India, Email: partha15baruah@gmail.com

Abstract

Assam has witnessed separatist movements and insurgencies since India's independence. The insurgency in the state began in 1979 with the formation of the 'United Liberation Front of Asom' (ULFA). ULFA has been fighting for Assam's sovereignty since its inception. The ULFA has surpassed several stages of political upheaval since its formation. On the creation of occasions, it even operated equal parts with the state machinery. This dynamic in the political history of ULFA itself is unique and reflects the subtle and underground outfits. This paper provides an understanding of the fractional differences of the ULFA to the Peace Accord between the Government and the organization. The paper is descriptive in nature and based on both primary and secondary sources of data.

Keywords : ULFA, Paradigm shift, Fractional differences, and Peace Accord.

1.1 Introduction

The United Liberation Front of Asom (ULFA), an insurgent organization, came into existence on April 7, 1979, at the deserted 'Rang Ghar' pavilion in Sivasagar. By waging an armed uprising against India, the ULFA sought to establish an independent and sovereign Assam. With the start of peace negotiations with the central government in 2011, ULFA underwent a major transformation, splitting into two factions after nearly three decades of struggle. The factions that emerged are ULFA (pro-talk) and ULFA (I). The faction involved in the peace talk referred to as ULFA (pro-talk), is headed by Chairman Arabinda Rajkhowa, while the anti-talk faction, ULFA (I), and is led by Commander-in-Chief Paresh Barua. In December 2023, a peace accord was signed between the pro-talks faction and the state and central government, leading to the disbandment of the ULFA Pro-Talk faction. The faction led by Paresh Baruah, referred to as ULFA (I), is still continues its operations its struggle. Therefore the main objective of the study is to examine the Factors behind the emergence of UFLA (I) and to understand the ULFA's peace agreement. Further, it tries to examine whether the initiative of peace talks or other factors was connected to factional differences between ULFA pro-talk and ULFA (I). What is the perspective of the organization's members regarding the peace agreement, and how does this agreement impact the community?

1.2 Context of the Study

ULFA was established in 1979, coinciding with the onset of the 'Assam movement', a six-year political campaign addressing the immigration issue to Assam from what is now Bangladesh. This influx, along with immigration from other regions of India, was causing the indigenous population of Assam to become a minority (Baruah, 1994). According to the ULFA, the Government of India has been continuously reshaping Assam's geographical landscape since the colonial period, which has negatively impacted the region's historically diverse ethnic groups (Borah, 2012). In this context, the ULFA presented two arguments: firstly, that Assam has never been a part of India, and secondly, that the Government of India has been capitalizing on Assam's rich natural resources since the British Raj, all the while neglecting to deliver any significant

benefits to the people living in Assam (Kotwal, 2011). Therefore, the ULFA led an armed struggle against the illegal occupation of Assam by India and the exploitative policies of the Central Government in New Delhi towards the resource-rich state of Assam to establish a Swadhin (Independent Assam) (Deka,2020). In April 1979, in Sivasagar, a group of young men shared their thoughts that the ‘All Assam Students Union’s’ (AASU) proposed agitation against immigrants would not work, that a simple agitation wouldn’t be effective; instead, they argued for a long-term solution, convinced that Delhi wouldn’t listen to peaceful demonstrations but would respond to a more aggressive approach (Hazarika, 2011). Therefore, they initiated a radical form of Movement under the banner of ULFA. They talked of the need for “a swadhin (independent) Assam, where ‘scientific socialism would be the way of life and where its natural resources would be exploited for the benefit of its people (ibid). Thus the ULFA developed during the Assam agitation based on ethnicity and ‘nationalist ideology’ (Gogoi, 2022).

In the initial years of its formation, the ULFA was able to gain some support from the people of different parts of Assam. It was involved in various local development activities and various communal activities of rural society such as building roads, embankments, schools, fisheries, and cooperative farming in agro-economics (Bhattacharya, 2023). ULFA took punitive measures against ‘anti-socials’ such as drunkards, gamblers, those selling illicit liquor, ‘morally loose characters’ as well as ‘fake ULFAs’ (Dutta, 2008). ULFA punished corrupt officials in Assam who misappropriated financial assistance meant for their development programs in view of their violent activities (Mahanta, 2012; Dutta 2020). In 1985, after the signing of the Assam Accord the newly formed Assam Gana Parishad came to power inspiring the people with hope for a new era of prosperity and stability. The formation of the AGP government was encouraging for the ULFA as it had known the AGP ministers since the days of the movement. Gradually, the ULFA leaders began to control the state administration (Kotwal, 2011) and started to engaged in many apolitical and conspiratorial activities. In 1988, the Chief Minister was aware of the activities of the ULFA cadres but failed to take action. As the situation in the state became unsettled, the Central Government dismissed the state government and introduced presidential rule. It was in November 1990 when President’s Rule was imposed under Article 356 of the

Indian Constitution, and a massive anti-insurgency operation, ‘Bajrang’, was launched. In April 1991, the military operation was called off, but on September 14, 1991, the army once again launched an operation named ‘Rhino’ (Sharma et al., 2008). Following these two operations, the Indian Government had declared the organization as outlaw. As the operation progressed from September 1991 to January 1992, ULFA agreed to negotiate for a peaceful settlement, but other factions of the organization dissatisfied with the prospect of a negotiated settlement, and refused to surrender arms (ibid). Again in Dec 2003 Operation ‘Flush Out’ had a large impact on the organizational structure of the ULFA, eventually leading to polarization in two different camps. In 2008, the declaration of ceasefire by the ‘A’ & ‘C’ company of the 28th Battalion of ULFA was an initial process of the above phenomena. Again on Dec-2009, certain founding leaders of the ULFA including the Chairman, Finance Secretary, and Foreign Secretary were detained & arrested in Bangladesh. The arrested leaders were later on released and the process of peace negotiation with the ULFA began. In 2011, the peace negotiation process started when the Pro talk faction of ULFA under Arabinda Rajkhowa and submitted demands to the central government. However, the ULFA ‘Commander-in-Chief’ Paresh Baruah had been resolutely opposing talks with the centre without addressing the issue of Assam’s sovereignty (Misra, 2009). Baruah renamed the organization as ULFA(I).

The ULFA split in 2011 when it started peace talks with the Indian Government. The organization split into two groups, those who wanted to enter into peace talks with the government and those who did not. One is the anti-talk faction led by the ‘Commander in Chief’ Paresh Baruah and the pro-talk faction led by Chairman Arabinda Rajkhowa. On February 5, 2011, leaders of ULFA, including ‘Vice President’ Pradip Gogoi, ‘Central Propaganda Secretary’ Mithinga Daimari and ‘Foreign Secretary’ Sashadhar Choudhary declared that ‘general council’ of the outfit had agreed to the ‘Central Executive Council’s (CEC) decision to engage in negotiation with the Central Government unconditionally. The group led by Paresh Baruah rejected the proposal and announced that the general assembly itself unconstitutional ((Bhattacharya, 2023).Baruah officially renamed ULFA (Independent) with the announcement of a new ULFA executive council with a new chairman by expelling Arabinda Rajkhowa in 2011.

The new executive council of the ULFA (I) had 16 members. Dr. Barman (Dr Mukul Hazarika) became the new acting chairman of the group. Paresh Baruah took over the dual responsibilities of the chief of the staff and the chairman of the group replacing. Jiban Moran was promoted to the rank of colonel and appointed finance secretary to the Head of the Finance Department. Bijay Chinese Das and Drishti Rajkhowa were also promoted to the post of ‘Deputy Commander in Chief’ of the outfit (ibid).

Thus, from the above discussion, it is observed that the ULFA has surpassed several stages of political upheaval since its formation. On the creation of occasions, it even operated equal parts with the state machinery. This dynamic in the political history of ULFA itself is unique and reflects the subtle and underground outfits. Meanwhile, the changing dynamics in the political history of ULFA reflect the paradigm shift within the ULFA. However, the year 2011 turned out to be important in the political history of ULFA as it was in 2011 that ULFA was split into two different factions formally. Although, the process of peace talks and factional differences has been going on since the early 90s, yet they got materialized only in 2010-2011 after the detained of certain top ULFA leaders. Therefore, it is in this context that we have made an attempt to study the factors behind the formation of ULFA (I) and the peace accord signed between the Government of India and ULFA.

1.3 Methodology

The study is an attempt to understand the Paradigm Shift of ULFA from Factional differences to the peace accord. In this study, we conducted our fieldwork from January 2024 to June 2024 in the Charaideo, Tinisukia, and Kamrup districts of Assam. The study is based on both primary and secondary sources of data. The secondary sources include books, published articles research papers, etc. The primary data was collected from field surveys. We have applied purposive sampling during the field visit. Four former male ULFA leaders were interviewed for the study. We have choose purposive sampling for our interviews as the interviewee are founding and leading members of the ULFA who have played a crucial role in the peace process from the negotiations all the way to the signing of the peace agreement. Additionally, many of these

interviewees are key figures in the ULFA (Independent) faction. Hence, the sample for the study includes former ULFA combatants from both faction ULFA (Pro-Talk) and ULFA (Independent). This study employs qualitative methods to help in gathering detail information about individual's perceptions, beliefs, opinions and emotions. The methods used to engage with the interviewee include in-depth personal interviews. The pattern of interview was unstructured with open ended questions. The interviews with each interviewee lasted 2 to 3 hours. The interviews with them were conducted entirely in Assamese. As the interviews were quite long, we asked if we could record them on our phone. Unfortunately, they weren't comfortable with that, therefore we wrote up everything down instead. We visited the interviewees at their residences. Prior to that, we reached out to them via phone, introduced ourselves and explained our purpose, and inquired about the best way to meet with them. They asked us a lot of questions during the phone call, including how we obtained their number, our reasons for wanting to meet, and the type of discussions we wished to have, among other things. We visited their homes after they provided us with their addresses. One of the primary challenges we faced at that time was that, even with their residential addresses, we had problem finding their houses. Additionally, we struggled with building rapport first. They found it difficult to communicate with us due to trust and understanding issue. But as the conversations went on, we observed a change for better. Despite encountering some challenges, their cooperation greatly facilitated the fieldwork.

1.4 Factional Differences: Formation of ULFA (I)

Examining the fluidity of structural dynamics in insurgent groups can offer us a deeper understanding of how they function, persist, and change over time. Their organizational identity is largely defined by their goals and ideologies. Although their goals and ideals are the same, they often face disagreements, factional splits, and, in the most drastic situations, complete organizational breakdowns (Morrison, 2017). Insurgent groups frequently encounter internal division, particularly when a faction decides to separate and create its own organization with its own leadership (Mahoney, 2017). The motivations for these splits can be diverse, stemming from political changes, strategic adjustments, negotiated agreements, or even conflicts between individuals (Morrison, 2017). Buke Richford (1989) states factionalism within an organization

that can lead to a split typically arises from calls for changes in policies or practices from specific sections. Furthermore, Joo and Mukharjee (2020) highlights that when rebel groups operate with a high level of command-and-control centralization, it can lead to a blame game among leaders as the group ages. This environment often encourages the supreme leader to consolidate power and limit the authority of other leaders. In turn, this can push the alienated leaders to break away and form their own rebel group. For example, the Irish Republican Army (IRA) faced a split due to disagreements over strategy, political goals, and leadership. This led to the formation of several splinter groups. At the end of 1969, the Official IRA divided into the Official IRA and the Provisional IRA, which then splintered further, resulting in the creation of groups like the Continuity IRA and the Real IRA. All three have played important roles in the ongoing conflict. Similarly, on April 30, 1988, two leading figures, Muivah and Swu, from the National Socialist Council of Nagaland (NSCN)—a rebel group that had been fighting with the Government of India since the 1970s—decided to part ways with the main NSCN due to political disagreements among the leaders. The split of the Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam (LTTE) (Sri Lanka) is also notable. The Eastern commander, Vinayaga moorthy Muralitharan, who is often referred to as Karuna, decided to go his own way. He created a military faction called the Tamil National Front and a political branch known as the Tamileela Makkal Viduthalai Puligal (TMVP), forming an alliance with the Eelam National Democratic Liberation Front (ENDLF). This division was largely fueled by disagreements between Karuna and LTTE leader Velupillai Prabhakaran, especially concerning the deployment of Eastern recruits to the North (Furman and Arulthas, 2021).

In the context of ULFA, on February 5, 2011, a significant announcement came from ULFA leaders, including ‘vice-chairman’ Pradip Gogoi, ‘foreign secretary’ Sashadhar Choudhury, and ‘central publicity secretary’ Mithinga Daimary. They revealed that the general council had agreed to engage in talks with the Central Government without any preconditions. However, Paresh Baruah, the ‘Commander-in-Chief’ of ULFA, and his faction rejected this decision, labeling the general council’s actions as unconstitutional. Then Paresh Baruah ‘expelled’ Arabinda Rajkhowa and appointed Abhijit Barman as the new ‘chairman’. This split resulted in two distinct factions:

ULFA (Pro talk) faction led by Arabinda Rajkhowa and the ULFA (Anti talk) faction led by Paresh Baruah. The anti talk faction later renamed it ULFA (I).

In view of exploring the nuance dynamics behind the split of ULFA (Pro -Talk) and ULFA (I), we tried to establish contacts with various founding members and leaders of ULFA (I). The changing dynamics within the ULFA since 2011 have opened up scope to study and discuss the transitional dynamics. Therefore, in my interaction with Drishti Rajkhowa,, we tried to explore the reasons behind the split of ULFA and the role of ULFA (I) in the present political scenario. According to him, (Drishti Rajkhowa)

In 2004, a significant seizure of 10 truckloads of weapons in Bangladesh had a considerable impact on the organization. By 2009, when Supreme Court judgment Paresh Baruaas the main accused he fled the country. In 2009, Dipyoti Mohanta, Chitraban Hazarika, Shashadhar Chowdhury, Raju Baruaand Arabinda Rajkhowa were incarcerated. By 2010, several battalions were actively involved in the peace process. In 2010, the organization disbanded its battalion and established two bases in Myanmar and Bangladesh. Mukul Hazarika became Chairman, Paresh Barua as C in C, Bijoy Chinese as Deputy C in C, and the group were officially declared as ULFA (I) in 2011.

Similarly, we also tried to explore the various transitional dynamics from Bijoy Chinese, According to him,

In 2008, a group declared a ceasefire with India, calling for our leader's participation. Although I came for a ceasefire, I moved back to Myanmar. At that point, I was the commander of the 28th Battalion. I discovered that our organization's members were dispersed. I reorganized and revived the organization, starting a new central committee and disciplinary staff. I became Deputy Commander in Chief of ULFA (I), which is now active.

From the narrative shared by former ULFA Deputy Commander-in-Chief Bijoy Chinese and Dristi Rajkhowa, it's evident that the roots of ULFA (I) can be traced back to the ceasefire

that began in 2008. This ceasefire led to significant structural changes within the organization, resulting in its regrouping and eventual transformation into ULFA (I). While ULFA (I) was officially declared in 2011, the groundwork for this new formation was laid in 2010. After the ceasefire involving A and C Companies, B Company and some members of C Company continued to operate within the 28th Battalion. Consequently, there was an effort to dissolve this company and reorganize the battalion under Bijoy Chinese's leadership. However, as of April 21, 2011, all ULFA battalions were disbanded, and the position of battalion commander was eliminated. Eventually, they decided to dissolve the battalion system and implement a new organizational structure. Since then, the military wing of ULFA has been split into two commands. The commands are known as the 'Eastern Command' and the 'Western Command'.

From the beginning, ULFA (I) posed new challenges for peace negotiation through acts of extortion and violence including a grenade explosion outside a crowded shopping mall in Guwahati in May 2019, and a bomb blast in Upper Assam on Republic Day in January 2020. Paresh Baruah created a major obstacle in the ongoing peace talk by demanding that the sovereignty of Assam be a precondition for talk.. On May 15, 2021, he announced a unilateral ceasefire for three months, citing the COVID-19 pandemic in Assam as the reason. On August 15, before Independence Day, the group released a statement extending the ceasefire for another three months. Meanwhile, the government attempted to persuade Paresh Barua to engage in peace talks with the help of mediators. He maintained that there is no possibility of the peace process with the government unless the issue of Assam's is included the agenda of the talks. In this context, Dristi Rajkhowa, the former 'Deputy Commander-in -Chief', shares the likelihood of ULF`A (I) engaging in peace talk as follows;

The aspiration for a fully sovereign Assam appears increasingly impractical, despite its distinct history from India. ULFA (I) may engage in peace talks if address self-determination and land rights for the indigenous Assamese people, ensuring exclusive land rights for them.

Similarly, Bijoy Chinese offers his insights as follows;

The organization will participate in peace talks centered on independence, with a focus on self-regulation and land rights. Achieving self-regulation, land rights, and inner line permits for Assam could lead to significant progress in negotiations. Notably, the recent ULFA agreement did not address land rights..

In the light of the narratives, it is found that without sovereignty, ULFA (I) is unlikely to come to negotiations. However, there is the possibility to advance the negotiation process on certain aspects such as the nation's right to self-determination, land rights, and issuance of inner-line permits. ULFA (I) refuses to start peace talks without talks on sovereign Assam. The ULFA (I) is still fighting for its demand of an 'independent sovereign Assam'. The ULFA (Pro-Talk) faction, who has been in peace negotiations with the Indian government since 2011, officially signed a tripartite peace agreement with the Center and the Assam government on December 29, 2023.

1.5 Exploring the Peace Process

Since 2011, after a long period of negotiations between the ULFA and the Government at various stages, the Peace agreement was signed in December 2023 between the ULFA, Assam, and the Government of India. In view of exploring the peace process and the accord, we interacted with Arabinda Rajkhowa the chairman of ULFA (Pro-talk) faction and Mrinal Hazarika commander of 28th Battalion who was leading cadre of ceasefire in 2008, to get a thorough understanding of this. After the official emergence of the ULFA in 1979, the organization launched and continued its armed struggle along various social welfare agendas. They participate in the various constructions of dirt roads or floodways in the village at the invitation of local organizers. In 1983, the ULFA began its transformation into an organized rebel group. In 1985 the AGP formed government in Assam and the ULFA took a new turn. The ULFA's violent activities began mainly during the 1980s and became more active after 1985, when the AGP came to power (Talukdar, 2017; Haloi, 2017). The violent activities of the ULFA became increasingly irresistible to the government. The deteriorating law and order situation in the state eventually forced the center to intervene and impose "Presidential Rule" in 1990. The

then Union Minister of the State for Home Affairs Subodh Kant Sahay said about the state government that the state machinery itself with the ULFA (Kotwal, 2001). On 27 November 1990 the ULFA was banned by the Government of India. Two days after the ULFA was banned, on 29 November 1990, the first major military operation against the ULFA, Operation Bajrang, was launched and the ULFA was banned. Since the 1990s, many army operations have been launched against the militant group in Assam and outside India. In 1991, he launched Operation Rhino against the organization. The operation continued from September 1991 to January 1992. Eventually, the counter-insurgency operation in Assam resulted in the arrest of 1,221 ULFA members in the early 1990s. In 1992, a group of ULFA members surrendered and decided to negotiate with the government (The Hindu, January, 04, 2024). Later, the group agreed to negotiate with the government for a peaceful settlement (Sarmah et al., 2008). In the context of the initial steps of ULFA into the ceasefire and negotiation process Mrinal Hazarika shares as follows;

In 1990, the ULFA was banned and presidential rule was introduced in Assam. The Indian government launched operations 'Bajrang' and 'Rhino'. Several ULFA leaders, including Pradeep Gogoi, Anup Chetia, and Shasadhar Chowdhury, were imprisoned during this period. In 1992, ULFA proposed talks, and the government sought negotiations through mediators, but leaders refused to accept arms surrender conditions, preventing further discussions.

The above narrative highlights that the ULFA's talks with the government first began during the military operations that started in the early 1990s. Civil society in Assam has had a major influence since ULFA first initiated this dialogue. In 1992, the peace talks with the government were sparked by the situation created by those military actions. However, the leaders refused the government's offer to surrender their weapons as a condition for starting negotiations, which ultimately brought the whole process to a standstill.

Later, the Counterinsurgency operations resulted in the arrest of 1,221 ULFA members. In 1991, Prime Minister Chandra shekhar informed the Rajya Sabha that the Union Government

would take necessary steps if the ULFA expressed willingness for political talks. The ULFA replied that no negotiations were possible as long as the army operation and presidential rule continued, and there would be no compromise on Assam's demand for 'sovereignty' In 1991, the Congress government led by Hiteswar Saikia took office. In 1991, Operation Rhino was launched against the ULFA. In January 1992, representatives of five top leaders, including General Secretary Anup Chetia, were involved in direct talks with Prime Minister PV Narasimha Rao. However, the talks did not proceed as Paresh Baruah refused to participate in the talks. Eventually, about 15 senior ULFA leaders led by Central Propaganda Secretary Sidharth Phukan surrendered to Chief Minister Hiteswar Saikia. In the context of their surrender, Mrinal Hazarika explains how the surrender of the member in the organization begins as follows;

In 1992, ULFA leaders Sidartha Phukon, Deputy C&C Kalpajyoti Neog, and General Secretary Anup Chetia participated in ceasefire discussions, but the leaders' refusal to accept disarming conditions led to Phukon and Neog's surrender, initiating the surrender process.

The narrative above highlights how the ceasefire in 1992 brought about a split between two factions: the ULFA and the Surrendered ULFA often referred to as 'SULFA' by the people of Assam. When the ULFA Executive Council chose not to participate in the ceasefire, pro-ceasefire leaders like Sidhartha Phukon and Kalpajyoti Neog, along with several cadres, decided to surrender to the Hiteswar Saikia Government. They were the pioneers of the first surrender process within the organization.

From April 1992 until January 1993 the Government of India again started a full-scale operation against ULFA due to its involvement in killings and abductions (Sarmah et al., 2008)). Under the circumstances, the ULFA has offered a set of three preconditions for dialogue and negotiations with the Government of India. These preconditions have been rejected by the government. The prerequisites are: (a) the negotiations should take place in a third country; (b) hold talks under the auspices of the United Nations supervision and (c) The agenda of the discussion included 'Sovereignty of Assam. In 2004, the ULFA dropped the first two

preconditions and offered to talk to the government. But the government makes it clear that the Government of India is not ready to discuss the issue of ‘sovereignty’. Later, the PCG formed and continued the negotiation process. A second step towards negotiation was taken when the ULFA nominated nine members from civil society on its behalf and formed the People’s Consultative Group (PCG) in 2005 to renegotiate with the government (Deka, 2020). The nine-member team of journalists, rights activists, lawyers, and educators created an environment for dialogue between the ULFA and the government (Hussain, 2006). There were three rounds of peace talks with the PCG on the release of ULFA’s top leaders from jail, and also to seek information on the cadres missing since 2003. After the Assembly election results, the two sides, the Government and the PCG, retained the third round of talks. During the crucial phase of the negotiations, a feeling of distrust prevailed between the two sides. In the third talks, Home Minister Shivraj Patil assured the delegation and issued an immediate appeal to both the ULFA and the government to observe restraint. But instead, a picture begins, within a fortnight of the joint statement, two ULFA cadres were shot dead in the Baksa district of Assam, followed by another incident in Meghalaya, where four cadres were killed (Bhattacharya, 2023). The ULFA has since launched retaliatory attacks. ULFA engaged in killings, extortion, and bomb blasts (Deka, 2020). Therefore, in September 2006, the army was forced to resume the operation. Police even arrested PCG members on various charges.

In the context of PCG initiative in peace talk, Mrinal Hazarika shares his insights on how the peace talk fell short, even with the PCG initiative as follows;

The PCG representative successfully convinced the government to discuss core issues, but the leaders didn’t send clear signals, leading to suspicion. The organization should have understood that the government wouldn’t sign a deal with a rebel group demanding sovereignty.

Hazarika’s account reveals that the PCG was able to persist with the negotiation efforts, but the leaders of the outfit were held back by ignorance and suspicion, which hindered progress. Consequently, no agreement or discussions have taken shape for a lasting peace. Therefore,

although the third phase of the negotiation process had been stalled, it resumed in 2008 with the 28th Battalion. The entire process was led by Jiten Dutta, Commander of 'A' & 'C' Company of the 28th Battalion. In 2006 and 2007, Mrinal Hazarika, Commander of the 28th Battalion, was arrested in Siliguri, West Bengal, and Prabal Neog, commander of the 28th Battalion, in Tezpur, respectively. The arrest of these two began drastic changes in the battalion. In 2007, Bijoy Chinese Das was appointed Commander of the 28th Battalion. While Bijoy Chinese was the commander of the 28th Battalion 'A' & 'C' companies Commander Jiten Dutta a declared ceasefire in 2008 without the permission of the top leadership of the organization. Jiten Dutta held a press conference at Amarpur on the Assam-Arunachal Pradesh Border on June 26 to formally clarify the ceasefire. In February 2008, leaders and members of the three companies gathered at the battalion's camp in Manbhum, Arunachal Pradesh to discuss the ceasefire. This was the first formal meeting regarding the battalion's move to a ceasefire (Gogoi, 2020). The first condition for the ceasefire of the 28th Battalion leaders was the release of imprisoned commanders Mrinal Hazarika and Prabal Neog. They also imposed a temporary suspension of army operations in Tinisukia district. At that time Hazarika and Neog were arrested inside the jail. They sent a letter to the government proposing a ceasefire. In this context Mrinal Hazarika shares about the ceasefire declared by 28th battalion as follows;

From 2003 to 2006, I held the position of Commander of the 28th Battalion, during which time we recognized the need for a significant policy change, but our concerns were dismissed by leadership. In 2007, I was arrested. In 2008, A and C Companies of the Battalion declared a ceasefire. I declared ceasefire from prison. After being released, they organized public meetings and reached out to leaders, but they refused to participate in negotiations. The 'A' and 'C' Companies presented a charter of demands to the government. The Organization expelled me, Prabal Neog, Jiten Dutta, and Jun Bhuyan and. The government refused to engage in discussions without central leaders' involvement.

Thus, the third phase of the negotiation process starts with the 'A' and 'C' companies of the 28th Battalion. On June 24, 2008, following the release of Mrinal Hazarika and Prabal Neog

from jail these companies of the ULFA 28 Battalion declared a unilateral ceasefire with the government. In 2009 both ‘A’ and ‘C’ company presented their charter of demand to the government. However, the organization disagreed and expelled Mrinal Hazarika, Jiten Dutta, and Jun Bhuyan from the primary membership of the organization. The discussions were called off by the government since the key leaders were not participating.

During the period of initiation of Ceasefire, in April 2009, Paresh Barua fled to Yunnan, a province in southwestern China, due to operations in Bangladesh. Once he left, the leaders of his group and some of their families went into hiding in places like Dhaka, Satcherry, and Sherpur (Bhattacharya, 2023). This situation left many ULFA cadres feeling lost about what to do next. When the Awami League came back to power in Bangladesh under Sheikh Hasina in 2009, a lot of ULFA members were forced out of the country. To avoid the risks they faced, the ULFA leaders in Bangladesh decided to take part in negotiations. But just before these talks could start, Chitraban Hazarika and Shashadhar Choudhuri were arrested at their homes on November 1st. Again, Arabinda Rajkhowa, Raju Barua, and their families were captured in Dhaka by a team from Bangladesh’s Rapid Action Battalion (ibid).

In 2009 the arrest and deportation of top leaders of ULFA to India by the Bangladesh government had provided a preliminary hope towards the revival of peace process. Meanwhile, the Intellectuals community of Assam took the lead in bringing the imprisoned ULFA leaders to the negotiating table (Gogoi, 2020). For, this purpose, they organized the views of civil society organizations in the state on the issue and asked the government to release the jailed ULFA leaders. They organized the views of civil society organizations in the state on the issue and asked the government to release them from jail soon. Thus, On 24 April 2010, representatives of civil society groups and prominent citizens gathered at the National Conference called Sammilita Jatiya Abhibartan in Guwahati under the leadership of Hiren Gohain. The session was attended by various prominent personalities and hundreds of civil society organizations. The conference called for the free passage and subsequent release of top ULFA leaders and was in favor of holding talks between the ULFA and the Indian Government, be it on any issue (Deka, 2020). At

that time, six leaders of the 15-member executive council of the organization were in judicial custody while Vice-President Pradip Gogoi and former Publicity Secretary Mithinga Daimari had already been released on bail. All the leaders in Assam agreed that the ULFA must engage in unconditional talks with the government. Among the issues to be discussed as preconditions was to precede with the peace talks without the sovereignty of Assam, for which Paresh Boruah refrained from participating.

In 2010, after extensive discussions by the expert committee, a twenty nine-page charter was presented to the government. It covered all the issues that had plagued Assam since the colonial era. The charter states that 'in protecting Indigenous identity and interests, the government should establish a version of dual citizenship, preventing the growing threat to the state and Indigenous people gaining political power to control their destiny as well as foreigners without a stake in long-term survival. The charter lays out a clear framework for managing the identification and prevention of foreign nationals within the state. It also emphasizes the recognition of six Indigenous communities, grants scheduled tribe status, ensures 88 percent of seats in elected bodies are reserved and enhances local resource control for these communities. This document includes all the suggestions from civil society organizations, which ULFA presents to the government as part of the 'Charter of Demand' (Bhattacharya, 2023). Although the session excluded the issue of sovereignty of Assam it insisted that all the core issues raised by the organization should be discussed. So, in 2010, after the presentation of the 'charter of demand', on 10 February 2011 the talks began. A suspension of activities agreement was signed between the ULFA and the State and Central Governments. The group said it would not surrender any weapons until a final agreement was confirmed. Each of the eight leaders was allocated a monthly stipend of Rs 80,000 and a Rs 3,000 stipend for the lower cadres admitted to the camp (ibid).

On December 27, 2023, ULFA signed a tripartite settlement memorandum with the Center and the Assam government, pledging to abandon violence, and integrate into mainstream society. The 12-year unconditional talks between the Arabinda Rajkhowa-led ULFA faction and the

government have ended. The chairman of the organization announced the official dissolution of the ULFA. As part of the peace agreement signed by the ULFA, it said its cadres would lay down arms and renounce all forms of violence, vacate their camps and join the democratic process. In the context of the agreement, Hazarika explains his views about the recently signed ULFA peace agreement as follows;

The negotiation process since 2011 has resulted in considerable exhaustion among stakeholders, leaving us unable to mobilize against the government. Consequently, we find ourselves without a voice or the ability to demand accountability from the Government of India even if the government fails to act on the issues mentioned for the economic and social advancement.

In contrast to Hazarika, ULFA Chairman Arabinda Rajkhowa briefly describes the agreement and its demands as,

I believe that the agreement between India and Assam will bring numerous benefits, including political representation for indigenous peoples and alleviating concerns over potential partition, relief from fear of partition, and promising projects like the Express Highway and Green Energy Project. The Indian government has also allocated Rs. 150 crore for socio-economic development.

In examining both narratives, it's apparent that ULFA (I) is unlikely to engage in negotiations without the issue of sovereignty being addressed. However, there is potential to make progress on certain fronts, such as the right to self-determination, land rights, and the issuance of inner-line permits. ULFA (I) insists that they won't start peace talks unless there's a conversation about a sovereign Assam. They continue to fight for their vision of an "independent sovereign Assam." In contrast, the ULFA (Pro-Talk) faction has been in peace negotiations with the Indian government since 2011 and officially signed a tripartite peace agreement with the Center and the Assam government on December 29, 2023.

1. 6 Conclusion

In light of the above discussion, it seems that the split within ULFA into the ULFA (Pro-Talk) and ULFA (I) factions occurred in 2011 when the Pro-Talk group started engaging in peace talks. However, this division didn't just pop up overnight; it was the result of a long series of events within the organization. The counterinsurgency efforts in the early 1990s led to some serious internal conflicts and strategic disagreements, particularly after the ceasefire declaration made by 'A' and 'C' Companies of the 28th Battalion of ULFA in 2008. After several leaders were arrested in 2009, a group of them decided to join the peace talks. While the Pro-Talk faction was negotiating with the government, another faction, led by Commander-in-Chief Paresh Baruah, chose not to participate in the talks. Instead, they rebranded themselves as ULFA (I) and continued their struggle. In 2011, the Pro-Talk faction officially announced their commitment to the peace talks with the government, doing so without any preconditions. On December 27, 2023, a significant tripartite agreement was signed after a decade of negotiations involving the ULFA, the Assam government, and the Central Government of India. This peace agreement with ULFA paves the way for a hopeful future of peace and development in Assam. It aims to help former ULFA members reintegrate into society by offering them rehabilitation opportunities. The agreement also emphasizes on accelerating the state's development and protecting the land and political rights of indigenous communities. Despite this, some ex-ULFA members have expressed concerns about how complete and effective this initiative truly is. Finally, achieving lasting peace in the region will depend on addressing the underlying issues, fostering economic growth, and encouraging social integration.

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